

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Novel Spanish Dataset for Financial Education Text Simplification Targeting Visually Impaired Individuals

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ABSTRACT Automatic Text Simplification (ATS) is a crucial task in natural language processing, aimed at making texts more comprehensible, particularly for specific groups such as individuals with visual impairments. One of the primary challenges in developing models for ATS is the scarcity of data, especially in Spanish. This manuscript introduces a novel dataset tailored for Spanish speakers with visual impairments, consisting of 5,314 pairs of original and simplified sentences created using established simplification rules. Additionally, we evaluate the feasibility of augmenting this dataset using large language models such as Generative Pre-training Transformer (GPT)-3, TUNER, and Multilingual T5 (mT5). We compare the simplifications generated by these models with our dataset to assess their effectiveness in data augmentation. The characteristics of our dataset and the findings from these comparisons are discussed in detail. The dataset is publicly available on Hugging Face at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/saul1917/FEINA>

INDEX TERMS Automatic text simplification, lexical simplification, word complexity, lexical complexity prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

ATS is a specialized area within Natural Language Processing (NLP) that converts complex texts into simpler versions, facilitating comprehension for readers with lower literacy levels [1]. Our study introduces a novel dataset designed explicitly for text simplification in Spanish. This original and simplified text pairs corpus has been meticulously

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curated to support developing and training advanced NLP models. Effective ATS methods require extensive parallel corpora comprising both standard and simplified texts to train simplification systems effectively [2]. ATS has diverse applications, including texts for non-native speakers [3] and individuals with cognitive disabilities such as autism [4], aphasia [5], and dyslexia [6]. Recent studies have expanded ATS applications further. The linguistic accessibility of Open Educational Resources for people with cognitive disabilities has been examined [7]. ATS has been adapted for deaf and

hard-of-hearing adults [8], and medical text simplification to improve patient access has been a focus [9]. Second language text simplification has been explored [10], and a dataset for word-complexity judgments from deaf and hard-of-hearing adults has been created [11]. Our study addresses the need for high-quality datasets and provides a novel resource for Spanish text simplification. This dataset, a collection of original and simplified text pairs, offers high-quality parallel corpora that fill a critical gap in resources available for Spanish text simplification. Including diverse topics ensures its applicability across various fields, enhancing its utility for academic research and practical applications. This dataset is particularly valuable for investigating thematic domains and providing content adapted for easier understanding for specific populations, primarily focusing on financial texts tailored for individuals with visual impairments. The practical implications are substantial, as it can directly contribute to developing more accessible technologies for visually impaired individuals.

Beyond its direct application in text simplification, this dataset has already been utilized in various research efforts focused on complex text detection, uncertainty estimation, and multilingual lexical simplification. One study explored using GPT-3 as a data augmentation tool to improve complex text classification [12]. Another work investigated uncertainty estimation methods for text complexity classification, using this dataset to evaluate different approaches [13]. Additionally, the dataset has been incorporated into a multilingual lexical simplification framework, contributing to broader research on text accessibility across multiple languages [14]. These studies demonstrate the dataset's role in enabling further advancements in text simplification and promoting collaborative research in the field.

Developing accessible technologies, especially in text simplification, for individuals with visual impairments is crucial. Studies have highlighted the challenges faced by those with Central Visual Field Loss (CFL) due to conditions like macular degeneration, showing that text simplification enhances reading performance by addressing specific lexical complexities [15]. An efficient text summarization method for blind individuals has been developed, which converts summarized content into speech for better information access [16]. Additionally, the difficulties encountered by blind users with out-of-vocabulary words on social media have been examined, emphasizing the need for advanced screen reader technologies [17]. Integrating these insights into text simplification tools can enhance readability and comprehension for visually impaired individuals, promoting greater inclusion and accessibility.

The main contributions of this paper are:

- We introduce a novel dataset designed explicitly for text simplification in Spanish, comprising original and simplified text pairs.
- We provide baseline metrics for text simplification in Spanish, serving as a benchmark for future research.

- We describe the dataset compilation process in detail and offer a comprehensive statistical overview of the data.
- The dataset, scripts, and annotation materials are available to the research community to encourage further advancements in the field.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides an overview of the state of the art in text simplification. Section III describes existing comparable resources for Spanish. Section IV presents the details of the compilation process of our dataset and experiments intended to serve as baselines for future research on the dataset. Finally, Section V discusses the baselines and the statistical analyses derived from the dataset.

II. STATE OF THE ART

A. TEXT AUTOMATIC SIMPLIFICATION AND DATASETS

Breakthroughs in text simplification have led to substantial advancements in NLP, transforming the field by improving text clarity and ease of access. These cutting-edge techniques, encompassing lexical, sentence-level, and document-level simplification, significantly improve text comprehension, keeping professionals at the forefront of the latest developments.

Lexical simplification involves substituting complex words with simpler alternatives, often leveraging large pre-trained models like Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) and GloVe for better context understanding [18]. Sentence-level approaches, such as those utilizing neural language models like T5 and BART, focus on restructuring sentences to maintain semantic integrity while simplifying syntax [19]. Document-level techniques address lexical and syntactic complexities by simplifying entire documents using rule-based and machine-learning methods [20]. These advancements make complex texts more accessible, particularly in specialized fields like medicine and education, thus promoting broader engagement and comprehension among diverse reader groups.

The innovations in dataset creation for text simplification have played a pivotal role in developing more effective and accurate models. These datasets are not just crucial, but they are the backbone of enhancing the accessibility and readability of complex texts. For instance, the MultiLS-SP/CA dataset is a game-changer [21]. It includes resources for lexical complexity prediction and simplification in Spanish and Catalan, filling a substantial gap in the available data for these languages. The ALEXSIS dataset, on the other hand, provides a comprehensive benchmark for lexical simplification in Spanish, with annotated instances that facilitate the training and evaluation of simplification systems [22].

Several significant corpora have been developed in the context of Spanish text simplification. The IrekiaLF_es corpus expands the available resources with meticulously aligned document-level and sentence-level corpora to ensure accuracy and utility in various research and practical applications [23]. These datasets address critical gaps in the

field, enabling more effective research and innovation and ultimately contributing to developing tools that improve text accessibility for diverse reader populations.

Despite the significant advancements, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations hindering the effectiveness and applicability of these datasets. It has been noted that while several resources exist for Complex Word Identification (CWI) and Lexical Complexity Prediction (LCP), there still needs to be more suitable data for Spanish. This scarcity challenges developing and evaluating robust lexical simplification and complexity prediction systems [21]. Additionally, shortcomings in the annotation and quality of lexical substitutions in the ALEXSIS dataset have been identified, indicating the need for a revised version with improved substitution quality [22]. These limitations underscore the need for further research and improvement in text simplification.

B. TEXT SIMPLIFICATION TARGETING VISUALLY IMPAIRED INDIVIDUALS

Text simplification makes content accessible to visually impaired individuals who often face challenges when reading standard texts. A text summarization method designed for blind individuals has been developed, leveraging text mining techniques to produce summaries converted into speech [16]. This approach is particularly beneficial as it addresses the accessibility needs of blind users by simplifying and summarizing complex information into more manageable formats. Additionally, the difficulties blind users encounter on social media due to the prevalence of out-of-vocabulary words have been explored, highlighting the importance of intelligent screen reader technologies that effectively manage these non-standard terms [17]. These studies underscore the necessity of developing robust text simplification and summarization techniques tailored to the unique needs of visually impaired individuals, thereby improving their access to information and digital content.

Text simplification targeting visually impaired individuals has shown promising potential in improving not only reading accessibility and comprehension but also social inclusion. Research emphasizes individuals' unique challenges with CFL due to conditions like age-related macular degeneration (AMD). Specific lexical simplifications—such as replacing low-frequency words with more common synonyms—have been shown to enhance reading speeds for CFL patients [15]. These findings highlight the importance of tailoring text simplification strategies to address the unique needs of visually impaired readers, thereby supporting the development of effective assistive technologies aimed at this population. By making digital content more accessible, text simplification can bridge the gap between visually impaired individuals and the digital world, fostering their social inclusion and connectivity.

Further supporting this approach, it has been discussed how text simplification can be customized for specific target audiences, including visually impaired individuals. This work uses sequence-to-sequence neural models to adapt texts for

FIGURE 1. Methodological process followed in this work.

different reading levels, which can be particularly beneficial for readers with visual impairments who require simplified texts to facilitate comprehension. By integrating these models with assistive technologies, it is possible to provide visually impaired users with more accessible content, enhancing their reading experience and overall accessibility [24].

III. METHODOLOGY

This study is divided into three methodological stages, aligned with the research questions outlined in Section I. Figure 1 shows the stages of the methodological process. Each of these stages is explained in this section. The first stage is the construction of a manual dataset. In this stage, we follow three steps described in the subsection “Manual Dataset Creation.” The first step is the definition of the sources to collect the information and the definition of the unit of analysis that we name text segment and how it is extracted from the text sources. The second step is the generation of rules to simplify the text segments. The last step is the operative process to create simple versions of the text segments. In this step, we explained who made the simplification and how they were prepared for this task.

Once the manual dataset is ready, the next stage involves generating additional dataset versions using trained models—including ChatGPT, mT5, and the TUNER system. In the subsection “Benchmarking against machine-augmented simplifications,” we describe the reason for selecting these models and how they were used to create simple versions of the original text segments. Finally, in the last stage, the quality of the manual and the machine-augmented datasets were compared using five types of metrics. The diagram shows examples for each metric, and in the subsection named “Quality Evaluation,” there is a description of how the metrics were obtained. The code developed for this work can be found

FIGURE 2. Dataset creation process developed in this work.

in https://gitlab.com/parma1/feina_financial_spanish_text_simplification

A. FINANCIAL EDUCATION TEXT DATASET CONSTRUCTION

Figure 2 comprises the process of building the text simplification dataset. This process is explained below:

As seen in the diagram, the first stage is the extraction of the texts, which begins with the search for the sources from which they will be extracted. A search was conducted on the internet to find books used for the dataset creation. The keywords used were “financial education” (in Spanish “educación financiera”). After the search, three criteria were applied for the books selection written in Spanish. The first criterion was that the content of the book should be oriented to educate the general population on how to manage personal finances. We discarded the books that were more oriented to university students or students who are learning advanced levels of Finance because the objective was to create a dataset to train models to simplify texts for the general population. The second criterion was related to the copyright of the book. We selected books of open access that let the copy of the content. After the application of the excluded criteria, four books were obtained [25], [26], [27], [28]. Then we extracted the text segments (sentences) from the books. A text segment is defined as follows: It is a piece of text that is separated from the next segment text by the following punctuation symbols: a) dot, b) semicolon, c) closing question mark, d) closing exclamation mark. In summary, we split the books into pieces of text that we called text segments. For example, in Table 1 we can see a paragraph decomposed into text segments, using the full stop.

TABLE 1. Examples of text segments extracted from a paragraph, with English translations.

Paragraph (Spanish)	Segments (Spanish)
	La tangibilidad es una característica muy esencial de un objeto para considerarlo bien económico.
La tangibilidad es una característica muy esencial de un objeto para considerarlo bien económico. Tangible es por consiguiente un computador, un carro, una casa, zapatos y muchísimas otras mercancías que son consideradas bienes económicos. Por otro lado, para que un producto adquiriera la categoría de bien económico, debe ser satisfactor de una necesidad o un deseo.	Tangible es por consiguiente un computador, un carro, una casa, zapatos y muchísimas otras mercancías que son consideradas bienes económicos. Por otro lado, para que un producto adquiriera la categoría de bien económico, debe ser satisfactor de una necesidad o un deseo.
Paragraph (English)	Segments (English)
	Tangibility is a key characteristic of an object that is considered an economic good.
Tangibility is a key characteristic of an object that is considered an economic good. A computer, a car, a house, shoes, and many other commodities are tangible and, therefore, considered economic goods. Moreover, to be categorized as an economic good, a product must fulfill a need or a desire.	A computer, a car, a house, shoes, and many other commodities are tangible and, therefore, considered economic goods. Moreover, to be categorized as an economic good, a product must fulfill a need or a desire.

In the second step, we formulated a set of clear, exemplified guidelines. These guidelines outlined the attributes within a text segment that required simplification and the necessary actions to craft a more concise text version. Our approach to designing these textual simplification guidelines was rigorous. We conducted an in-depth review of existing literature, specifically focusing on the Simplext corpus developed by the Diles Group at the Autonomous University of Madrid [29].

Building upon the insights gained from our literature review and the analysis of the Simplext corpus, we selected and refined a set of simplification guidelines tailored to the needs of visually impaired individuals. These guidelines were designed to follow a structured, sequential approach to ensure consistency and avoid omissions. The application order prioritizes lexical transformations first, followed by syntactic modifications and discourse-level adjustments, such as punctuation. This systematic organization minimizes conflicts between guidelines and enhances clarity in simplification.

Rather than adopting the Simplext guidelines in their entirety, our interdisciplinary team reviewed and selected those deemed most relevant for our target population. The definitions were adapted, and illustrative examples from financial education texts were incorporated to clarify the simplification process. This refinement ensured that the guidelines effectively improved readability while maintaining textual meaning. The validation process aligned the selected guidelines with theoretical principles and practical considerations for visually impaired readers. Each guideline was formulated to address a distinct linguistic attribute, preventing unnecessary repetition and preserving the integrity of the message.

Throughout this process, the interdisciplinary team received continuous guidance from a researcher specializing

in linguistics and accessible text processing alongside expert advisors in disability and finance. The simplifications underwent qualitative review to ensure their effectiveness, and workload distribution was carefully managed to maintain quality control and adequate supervision.

This literary exploration was further enriched by consultations with specialists in text adaptation for the visually impaired and linguistic experts, ensuring that the simplification guidelines aligned with best practices for readability and accessibility.

Table 13 of the Appendix shows an extract from the manual. The second column of the appendix has the name of attributes that should be simplified, and the third column has a summary of the instructions used to solve the complexity generated by the attribute. For example, the first attribute in column two is named “word frequency” and the instruction in the third column is to replace low-frequency words with commonly used words. In summary, these instructions are the guidelines to generate simple text segments from the original text segments. A total of 21 attributes with their instruction were generated.

The final step is the text simplification (annotation). For this task, six advanced philology students were recruited from 25 candidates to simplify text segments using a manual, producing 5,314 pairs of complex/straightforward text segments. The selection criteria included high academic performance in key linguistics courses (morphology, semantics, lexicology, syntax, discourse modalities, general linguistics, and written expression) and prior experience in text editing, proofreading, or academic publishing.

In order to avoid or at least reduce the labeling bias due to the subjectivity of the annotators there was a training session with the annotators before the beginning of the annotation phase. In that session, they were trained not only in the way the work was organized (assignment of items, a tool where the annotation is added, control and review of the annotation, etc.) but also on how to carry out the annotation properly with examples of situations that can arise and how to deal with them. In the session, an annotation practice with the same examples for all the annotators was carried out. Then, the annotation was shared, and the differences were analyzed and discussed. When the annotation phase began the annotators had on hand the list of rules of the text simplification with examples for each rule. Besides, during the annotation phase, a research team supervisor with experience in linguistics addresses questions and provides feedback and corrections to the annotators when required.

The most frequent attributes requiring simplification were unnecessary words, sentence length, and complex phrases, as depicted in Table 2. Less common attributes, like ambiguity in word meaning and subordinating conjunctions, appeared less frequently in our manual annotations, despite their potential impact on readability. The dataset, potentially biased towards more prevalent attributes, reflects the domain-specific nature of the source texts. For example, the abstract nature of finance implies less frequent use of

TABLE 2. Distribution of sentences among different linguistic features.

Feature	No. of Sentences	Percentage (%)
Subjunctive Mood Verb Forms	18	0.7
Use of Nominalizations	48	1.8
Common Discourse Markers	65	2.5
Past Anterior and Future Perfect Tense	67	2.6
Conjunctions	116	4.4
Subordinating Conjunctions	195	7.5
Abstract vs. Concrete Language	196	7.5
Abbreviations-Shortenings	223	8.5
Visual Reference Dependence	272	10.4
Use of the Gerund	317	12.1
Ambiguity in Word Meaning	469	17.9
Use of Numerical Expressions	473	18.1
Relative Clauses	530	20.3
Sentences of Formal and Aesthetic Use	656	25.1
Sentence Order	722	27.6
Use of Complex Punctuation Marks	809	30.9
Word Frequency	988	37.8
Parenthetical Phrases	1047	40.1
Complex Phrases	1483	56.7
Sentence Length	1649	63.1
Unnecessary Words	2490	95.2

visual reference dependence compared to longer sentence structures typical of financial jargon. The final dataset, including original texts, simplified versions, and identified attributes, is available online.

B. BENCHMARKING AGAINST MACHINE-AUGMENTED SIMPLIFICATIONS: GPT-3, TUNER AND mT5

Different methods for text simplification have been developed in the literature, with different approaches; from rules-based systems to Large Language Model (LLM). To identify what models are worth to test, we developed a small qualitative test, with the simplification of 13 text segments using the following systems: GPT-3 [30], mT5 [31], TUNER [32], FastChat [33], Alpaca13b [34] and Llama 13b [35]. The choice of these models was guided by the need to examine a range of simplification methodologies. GPT-3 represents a state-of-the-art generative approach that produces fluent and contextually coherent simplifications [36]. TUNER employs a hybrid strategy integrating rule-based mechanisms with statistical techniques to refine lexical substitutions [37]. mT5, as a multilingual transformer model, allows for a comparative analysis between a general-purpose sequence-to-sequence approach and models tailored for Spanish text simplification [31]. This selection ensures a diverse evaluation of rule-based, neural, and multilingual simplification paradigms.

A sample of the results can be seen in Table 14 in the Appendix. In most of the examples GPT-3 outputs the most aggressive simplifications, shortening the text segments considerably and keeping the main idea of the segments. Llama generates inconsistent text segments, occasionally inserting words in English. Alpaca also presents results with low semantics correctness. Similarly, FastChat fails to deliver semantically correct results. mT5 and TUNER delivered semantically and syntactically correct results. mT5 was able to generate more simplified text segments compared to Tuner, as the former is more conservative due

TABLE 3. Examples of simplifications by GPT-3, mT5, and TUNER, with english translations.

Original (Spanish)	Simplifications (Spanish)
Si tuviera una computadora mejor, me sentiría motivado para trabajar en proyectos paralelos.	simpleGPT3: Me sentiría motivado para trabajar en proyectos paralelos si tuviera una computadora mejor.
	mT5: Si tuviera una computadora mejor, trabajaría motivado en proyectos paralelos.
	TUNER: Si tuviera una computadora mejor, me sentiría motivado para trabajar en proyectos de investigación.
Original (English)	Simplifications (English)
If I had a better computer, I would feel motivated to work on side projects.	simpleGPT3: I would feel motivated to work on side projects if I had a better computer.
	mT5: If I had a better computer, I would be motivated to work on side projects.
	TUNER: If I had a better computer, I would feel motivated to work on research projects.

to its rule-based approach. Based on our evaluation, GPT-3 yielded the best results in terms of correctness, semantic preservation, and simplification. Also TUNER and mT5 achieved outputs with considerable correctness, unlike the rest of the models (FastChat, Llama and Alpaca), which often failed in producing syntactically and semantically correct outputs. Other LLMs were tested: Bard does not work in Spanish by the writing time of this work, Mosaic MPT-7B model (see <https://huggingface.co/spaces/mosaicml/mpt-7b-chat>) did not work well in our preliminary tests. From the previous analysis we decided to select GPT-3, mT5 and TUNER for the second step.

A comparative analysis of the models revealed differences in their simplification strategies. GPT-3 demonstrated strong lexical and syntactic simplification capabilities, restructuring sentences for improved readability while maintaining fluency. Its simplifications sometimes required further refinement to enhance clarity and accuracy. By contrast, mT5 prioritized fidelity to the original text, making only minor modifications. While this approach preserved the source structure, it resulted in limited simplifications. Meanwhile, TUNER made minimal changes and, at times, did not modify the text. When it did, however, it occasionally introduced substitutions that altered meaning or led to grammatical inconsistencies. These tendencies can be observed in Table 3, which presents examples of simplifications generated by each model, including their English translations for clarity.

As a second step in the implemented methodology of this work, we evaluated GPT-3, mT5 and TUNER to perform automatic text simplification. We aim to evaluate the quality of each one of the tested models against the manually generated data. This can shed light on how close automatic systems are to manual simplifications in a specific domain such as finance education for blind people. Data augmentation policies for example can be formulated upon the measured performance.

Therefore, we generated the additional text-simplifications datasets

- Financial Education Text Dataset simplified by TUNER: built using the TUNER system developed in [32].
- Financial Education Text Dataset simplified by mT5: Generated with the mT5 simplification model proposed in [38].
- Financial Education Text Dataset Simplified with GPT-3: using the GPT-3 model described in [30]. By the time of writing this work, the model was not available for free usage by OpenAI. We used the following prompt *Simplifique el siguiente texto en español:*. Only one prompt result for each input segment was included in the dataset.

C. QUALITY EVALUATION OF THE DATASETS

Three kind of evaluations were carried out. First, automatic simplicity metrics were computed for each dataset. As previously mentioned, we categorized these metrics into three classes. The following subset of metrics were selected for each class:

- Reference-less metrics for single text segments: We selected specific metrics for Spanish: the Fernandez-Huerta (lower values represent more difficult text), Szigriszt Pazos indices (lower values represent more difficult text), Gutierrez-Polini (Higher values represent a more difficult text) and Crawford (Higher values represent a more difficult text). As complementary measurements, we also report the number of mono and polysyllables, as also the number of syllables and words. The metrics of this category were imported from the *TextStats* package <https://pypi.org/project/textstat/> [39].
- Reference-less simple/complex comparison metrics: As for the previously mentioned metrics which account for a comparison between the simple and complex sentences, we measured the compression ratio, number of sentence splits, the Levenshtein similarity index, the number of exact copies and the additions and deletions performed. We used the Easier Automatic Sentence Simplification Evaluation (EASSE) python package [40] to calculate them. To measure the semantic preservation, we used the cosine distance between the BERT model trained on a big Spanish corpus (BETO) embeddings of the simple and complex sentences. BETO is a BERT architecture pre-trained in a Spanish corpus [41]. For sentence embedding extraction we used the library developed in [42] along with the weights of BETO, made available in [espejelomar/sentece-embeddings-BETO](https://github.com/espejelomar/sentece-embeddings-BETO) through the HuggingFace application programming interface.
- Reference based metrics: As for the quantification of text simplicity based upon 2 or more human created references, we use the System output Against References and against the Input sentence (SARI) and bilingual evaluation understudy (BLEU) scores. We used the

implementations of these metrics provided also in the EASSE python package.

- As a complementary reference-based measurement, we present metrics of discrimination between the complex and simple text segments to determine how much the simplified sentences differ from the original ones. The discrimination metrics are the average Accuracy and F1 score of Random Forest and BETO models trained with each dataset to classify the text segments into simple or complex (the complex is the original text segment). A higher Accuracy or F1 score of the classifier means that the text segments simplified are easy to discriminate from the original segments.

We fine-tune the BETO model for the binary classification into simple and complex with each dataset. The Random Forest were also trained for the same tasks with each dataset, using TF-IDF. The training was executed with 10 partitions (cross-validation train/test) that were the same for each dataset. Therefore, the index of the text segments in the training and testing were the same between models. The average accuracy and F1 score of tests were presented as metrics of discrimination between the complex and simple text segments.

In the case of BETO models, the best values of the hyperparameters learning rate, weight decay, batch size, and the scheduler were selected using weights and biases suite with Bayesian optimization. The training dataset in each partition was divided into two subsets: one subset to compute the weights of the last layer of BETO (75% of the training dataset, 3986 observations) and the other part (25% of the training dataset, 1328 observations) to define when the model should stop the training using early stopping with a patience value of 2 of the cross-entropy loss function. In the case of Random Forest models, we selected the best values of the number of trees, maximum number of features, and minimum sample of leaf, using Bayesian optimization and cross-validation of 5 folds with each training dataset.

Finally, to incorporate human judgment of the text segments for each system and the manual simplifications, we solicited feedback from two visually impaired subjects on the simplification quality of $N = 100$ text segments. Both subjects possess extensive expertise in text simplification tailored for blind or visually impaired audiences. Additionally, one of the judges has a degree in Business Administration, which allows her to evaluate the transcription of financial terms. Both judges provided their input after completing an informed consent form, ensuring adherence to the ethical considerations of their participation in this study segment. Each evaluator was asked to reply the following evaluation criteria:

- The output text segment is simpler than the original?
- The output text segment is simpler preserves the meaning of the original?
- The output text segment is better understood than the original?

TABLE 4. Statistics for the manually simplified dataset. Note: columns μ_s and σ_s indicate the mean and standard deviation of the simplified text segments, respectively, while μ_c and σ_c represent the same statistics for the original (complex) text segments.

	μ_s	σ_s	μ_c	σ_c
fernandez_huerta	87.13	14.88	79.09	20.16
szigriszt_pazos	83.68	15.12	75.88	20.11
gutierrez_polini	39.38	6.95	37.46	8.33
crawford	3.41	1.32	3.72	1.20
syllable count	37.51	22.73	46.12	27.51
word count	22.01	13.14	27.59	16.03
poly count	4.32	3.27	5.11	3.82
mono count	12.27	7.82	15.97	9.63

- The output text is more suitable than the original for blind or visually impaired people?

The items were answered by the two judges using a Likert scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means total agree with the affirmation of the item, 2 agree, 3 neutral, 4 disagree and 5 totally disagree. For each source text segment, four simplification proposals were presented to the judges: the manual proposal, the GPT-3, TUNER and mT5 outputs. The four text simplification proposals were sorted randomly to neutralize a possible initial order effect.

IV. RESULTS

In Subsection IV-A the results for the calculated metrics are depicted. We develop the corresponding analysis in order to shed light about the quality of the automatic simplifications.

A. SIMPLIFICATIONS METRICS FOR THE MANUAL AND AUTOMATIC SIMPLIFICATION DATASETS

The first set of experiment results show the output of computing the different reference-less lexical simplicity metrics, the simple/complex comparison of the text segments with no reference, and the reference based metrics, as described in Section III-C. We calculate such measures to quantitatively compare how the simplification was carried out for the different tested systems. We also compute the metrics for the manually simplified dataset as a reference. Therefore we include the results for the Manual, GPT-3, mT5 large and TUNER. Finally the results for the human based judgements of a subset of text segments for each generated dataset are described. Tables 4, 5, 6 and 7 describe the yielded results of the selected lexical reference-less metrics. As previously mentioned, the Fernandez-Huerta, Szigriszt-Pazos, and Gutierrez-Polini metrics, with higher values, indicate better simplification. As for the word count, polysyllable count in general, the lower, a better text simplification, with a number of exceptions.

Table 4 shows the lexical complexity metrics for both the simple and complex sentences from the manually simplified dataset. As for the Fernandez-Huerta, Szigriszt-Pazos and the Gutierrez-Polini metrics, a trend where its values are higher in average for the simple sentences can be seen. Using a

TABLE 5. Statistics for the GPT-3 text simplifications. Note: columns μ_s and σ_s indicate the mean and standard deviation of the simplified text segments, respectively, while μ_c and σ_c represent the same statistics for the original (complex) text segments.

	μ_s	σ_s	μ_c	σ_c
fernandez_huerta	83.44	14.20	82.40	17.65
szigriszt_pazos	80.14	14.41	79.14	17.66
gutierrez_polini	38.91	6.73	38.55	7.43
crawford	3.71	1.15	3.61	1.17
syllable count	39.03	13.07	48.97	27.61
word count	23.37	7.59	29.36	16.13
poly count	4.26	2.33	5.41	3.86
mono count	13.45	5.06	17.04	9.74

Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney statistical significance test, all of the aforementioned metrics present a statistically significant difference between the simple and complex tests. This using a confidence interval of 95%.

A similar behavior is described in Table 6 for the GPT-3 generated dataset, where all the derived metrics yield a higher value for the simple sentences. Also, statistical significance of such metrics between the average of the simple and complex sentences is achieved. The average difference for the derived metrics between the simple and complex sentences is slightly lower when compared to the results yielded in the manually generated dataset. This suggests that manually simplification is better than the GPT-3 generated simplifications.

The Tuner generated dataset exhibits a weaker lexical simplification effectiveness, as seen in Table 7, where the average difference between the derived metrics for the simple and complex sentences is lower when compared to the GPT-3 and Manually generated dataset.

As for the mT5 simplified dataset, the trend of higher values for the simplified sentences is also visible as seen in Table 5. However, in this case there is no statistical significance for all of them. This according to the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test carried out.

The highest improvements in lexical simplicity according to the tested metrics were yielded by the manually and GPT-3 generated datasets by a considerably larger margin. Both TUNER and mT5 achieved the lowest values, suggesting that both systems are considerably worse at lexical simplification.

B. SIMPLE-COMPLEX COMPARISON BASED METRICS

Table 8 shows the simple-complex comparison based metrics calculated for the 4 datasets: the compression ratio, the number of sentence splits, the Levenshtein similarity, the number of exact copies, the additions/deletions proportion, the lexical complexity score and the BERT and BETO based similarity scores. For the compression ratio, the Manually and GPT-3 generated datasets show a clear lead over the mT5 and TUNER generated datasets. This suggests how the two former systems are not as effective as the manual and GPT-3 based simplifications, from a lexical simplification

TABLE 6. Columns μ_s and σ_s indicate the mean and standard deviation of the simplified text segments, respectively, while μ_c and σ_c represent the same statistics for the original (complex) text segments.

	μ_s	σ_s	μ_c	σ_c
fernandez_huerta	86.02	16.73	79.09	20.16
szigriszt_pazos	82.67	16.97	75.88	20.11
gutierrez_polini	39.55	7.66	37.46	8.33
crawford	3.44	1.40	3.72	1.20
syllable count	37.41	23.48	46.12	27.51
word count	22.22	13.57	27.59	16.03
poly count	4.18	3.33	5.11	3.82
mono count	12.64	8.06	15.97	9.63

TABLE 7. Statistics for the TUNER text simplifications. Note: Columns μ_s and σ_s indicate the mean and standard deviation of the simplified text segments, respectively, while μ_c and σ_c represent the same statistics for the original (complex) text segments.

	μ_s	σ_s	μ_c	σ_c
fernandez_huerta	85.80	16.17	82.13	17.52
szigriszt_pazos	82.48	16.31	78.86	17.52
gutierrez_polini	39.93	7.11	38.49	7.38
crawford	3.44	1.20	3.64	1.14
syllable count	50.48	28.99	49.20	27.62
word count	30.17	16.80	29.48	16.12
poly count	5.52	4.04	5.44	3.87
mono count	17.21	9.97	17.10	9.73

perspective. The Sentence-BERT (SBERT) and Sentence-BETO (SBETO) based similarity scores suggest that the semantics of the simplified text segments are fairly similar for the GPT-3 and manual simplifications, which advocates for a consistent simplification process of both systems. For TUNER and mT5, the high SBERT and SBETO similarity scores, along with a high compression ratio and frequent exact copies, suggest that these systems fail to provide adequate text simplification.

Table 8 also shows that the *exact copies* metric for the GPT-3 and manual simplification systems are 0 for both, meaning that there is always an effective text transformation performed in both cases. The proportion of additions and deletions for GPT-3 and the manual outputs also correlates with this trend, as both generate text segments with significantly higher transformations of both types, when compared to the TUNER and mT5 systems. The Levenshtein similarity score strengthens this argument, showing lower scores for the manually and GPT-3 when compared to the mT5 and TUNER systems. Finally, according to the lexical complexity score, also the GPT-3 and Manual systems managed to generate less lexically complex text segments, when compared to the TUNER and mT5 systems. A similar trend regarding the *sentence splits* metric is revealed, where the manually and GPT-3 systems are able to perform more sentence splits when compared to the TUNER and mT5 systems.

TABLE 8. Results for all the tested systems using the reference-less comparison based metrics. Value pairs in the same row underlined or with * are not statistically different according to the Wilcoxon test, with a $p = 0.05$.

	Manually Ds.	GPT-3 Ds.	TUNER Ds.	mT5 Ds.
Compression ratio	<u>0.84±0.05</u>	<u>0.84±0.13</u>	1.02±0.01	0.89±0.03
Sentence splits	<u>1.36±0.49</u>	1.16±0.59	1.26±0.27	0.9±0.1
Levenshtein similarity	<u>0.76±0.03</u>	0.77±0.03	0.94±0.01	0.91±0.02
Exact copies	<u>0.00±0.0</u>	0.00±0.0	0.37±0.23	0.29±0.21
Additions proportion	0.18±0.02	0.16±0.03	0.07±0.01	0.05±0.01
Deletions proportion	<u>0.37±0.04</u>	0.34±0.04	0.05±0.01	0.17±0.04
Lexical complexity score	<u>9.55±0.58</u>	<u>9.55±0.59</u>	9.61±0.45*	9.62±0.44*
Sbert cos. sim.	0.87±0.01	0.89±0.01	0.97±0.00	0.94±0.01
Sbeto cos. sim.	0.92±0.01	0.92±0.01	0.98±0.00	0.96±0.00

TABLE 9. Average and standard deviation of the SARI scores for the simplified text segments generated by the manual, GPT-3, TUNER and mT5 systems. The higher the better.

N. r.	N.	Manual	GPT-3	mT5	TUNER
2	149	<u>48.7±12.6</u>	41.6±12.2	34±11.3	26.4±7.9
3	134	<u>48.2±11.9</u>	42.4±11.7	34.1±11.4	26.7±8.1
4	119	<u>48.1±11.9</u>	42.1±11.3	33.9±11.2	26.7±8.2
5	94	<u>48.8±10.7</u>	41.1±10	34.4±11.1	27.4±8.5

For the 9 tested simple-complex text segment based metrics we carried out a normality and homoscedasticity (equal variances) statistical test, to choose which statistic tests to use to compare these 9 variables across the 4 treatments (manually, mT5, TUNER and GPT-3 simplified text segments) used in the experimental setting. We used the pingouin python package (see <https://pingouin-stats.org/build/html/index.html>) to implement the normality and the homoscedasticity tests. According to them, none of the variables for the 4 treatments are normal or full-fill homoscedasticity. Therefore we chose to carry out a Wilcoxon signed test.

Table 8 shows the statistical analysis using the aforementioned Wilcoxon test of all the datasets for each of the 9 evaluated metrics. Value pairs within the same row underlined or with the * symbol are not statistically significant according to the Wilcoxon signed test. It describes how for every comparison between text simplification systems, there is a statistically significant difference, except in the case when comparing the compression ratio between the manually and the GPT-3 generated datasets. Finally, when comparing the mT5 and the TUNER datasets, the lexical complexity score is also not statistically significantly different.

In summary, according to Table 8 we can consider that the manual simplifications are slightly better according to the Levenshtein similarity, *sentence splits* and the number of deletions and additions, when compared to the GPT-3 based simplification system. As for the compression ratio and lexical complexity score, the GPT-3 system performs very similar when compared to the manual simplifications. Both the manual and GPT-3 text simplifications are considerably better compared to the TUNER and mT5 simplifications.

C. REFERENCE BASED METRICS

As for the reference based metrics SARI and BLEU, are depicted in Tables 9 and 10, respectively. Specifically

TABLE 10. Average and standard deviation of the BLEU scores for the simplified text segments generated by the manual, GPT-3, TUNER and mT5 systems. N. r. stands for the number of reference sentences, and N. the total number of sentences. The higher the better. Value pairs underlined are no statistically different according to the Wilcoxon test with a $p = 0.05$.

N. r.	N.	Manual	GPT-3	MT5	TUNER
2	149	49±23.1	44.9±22.1	<u>56.4±17.8</u>	51.1±17.7
3	134	48.5±22.5	45.5±22.1	<u>56.2±17.1</u>	51.4±17.1
4	119	<u>47.5±22.3</u>	<u>44.9±22.1</u>	<u>54.9±17</u>	50.4±17.1
5	94	<u>47.9±20.9</u>	44.81±21.6	<u>55.6±16</u>	51±15.2

TABLE 11. 10-Folds mean statistics of the accuracy and F1-score for the BETO based classifier and random forest model with a TF-IDF based representation. Value pairs underlined are no statistically different according to the Wilcoxon test with a $p = 0.05$.

Dataset	BETO		Random Forest	
	Acc.	F1-score	Acc.	F1-score
Manual	<u>0.830±0.012</u>	<u>0.830±0.012</u>	0.681±0.011	<u>0.681±0.011</u>
GPT-3	0.753±0.009	0.750±0.010	0.637±0.010	0.636±0.012
mT5-large	<u>0.724±0.012</u>	0.697±0.010	0.600±0.019	0.597±0.018
TUNER	0.744±0.006	0.765±0.008	0.630±0.007	0.629±0.007

TABLE 12. Average of human scores based judgements using the Likert scale. The lower the better. Value pairs in the same row underlined or with * are not statistically different according to the Wilcoxon test, with a $p = 0.05$.

	Manually Ds.	GPT-3 Ds.	TUNER Ds.	mT5 Ds.
Judge1				
Simplicity	<u>1.83±1.19</u>	<u>1.83±1.26</u>	4.30±1.09	2.62±1.81
Meaning Pres.	<u>1.46±1.30</u>	<u>1.67±1.30</u>	3.37±1.66*	3.44±1.79*
Understand.	<u>2.05±1.30</u>	<u>1.93±1.22</u>	4.26±1.14	2.93±1.70
Suitability	<u>2.00±1.35</u>	<u>2.57±1.48</u>	4.34±1.12	2.96±1.72
Judge2				
Simplicity	<u>2.46±1.48</u>	<u>2.39±1.48</u>	4.55±0.94	3.46±1.51
Meaning Pres.	<u>1.99±1.44</u>	<u>2.07±1.54</u>	4.02±1.50*	4.00±1.40*
Understand.	<u>2.59±1.45</u>	<u>2.57±1.48</u>	4.58±0.87	4.01±1.29
Suitability	<u>2.56±1.44</u>	<u>2.53±1.43</u>	4.55±0.88	4.02±1.26

for the BLEU metric, Table 10 reveals that the manual simplifications perform best through all the dataset variation cases: using two text segment references (with a sample size of 149 observations) up to five text segment references (with a sample size of 94 observations). The comparison of the references with the manual dataset is meant to evaluate how consistent is the human simplification. It can be considered a reference value for both reference based metrics. In second place, the GPT-3 simplifications are the better ones, using the SARI metric according to Table 9 for all the tested datasets with 2 to 5 references. The decrease of the SARI value when compared to the manual simplifications is around 6 units. In third place, the mT5 simplifications yield a value near to 33, for all the tested dataset samples with different number of references. Similarly, a drop of around 6 units for the SARI metric is perceived between the GPT-3 and mT5 simplifications. Finally, the simplifications with the lowest SARI values in average, were yielded by the TUNER system.

As for the statistical relevance of the difference between each system according to the SARI and BLEU metrics, we verified that nor the BLEU or SARI metric present a normal distribution and equal variances for both the manual and GPT-3 systems. Therefore, similar as the previous set of metrics, we executed a non-parametric Wilcoxon signed test

TABLE 13. Attributes and guidelines for simplifying discourse segments of financial texts for visually impaired individuals.

Original	Attribute	Guideline for simplification
1	Word Frequency	Replace low-frequency words with commonly used words.
2	Abstract vs. Concrete Language	When possible, replace words with abstract or less imaginable referents with concrete or imaginable referents. It can be suppressed if the word is in an unnecessary idea to convey the message.
3	Visual Reference Dependence	When possible, replace discourse segments with visual references. It can be suppressed if the word is in an unnecessary idea to convey the message.
4	Ambiguity in Word Meaning	Replace polysemic words according to their main meanings.
5	Unnecessary Words	Eliminate words and phrases that are not necessary for understanding the message of the text.
6	Complex Phrases	Replace phrases (complex lexical expressions) with their one-word equivalents.
7	Use of Nominalizations	Replace nominalizations with verbs that express the same states, processes, and actions.
8	Conjunctions	Coordinating: Preferably use the conjunctions "y" and "ni". However, replacement is unnecessary in short sentences and those that do not employ other attributes that make the text difficult. Disjunctive : Use the conjunction "o". However, modification is only recommended when the marker is infrequently used or when a less explanatory style is used for a financial education text. Adversative : Use the conjunction "pero" in affirmative constructions and "sino" in negative constructions. However, modification is only recommended when the marker is infrequently used or when a less explanatory style is used for a financial education text. Other Coordination Connectors: Modify these coordination links only when the marker is infrequently used or when a less explanatory style is used for a financial education text.
9	Subordinating Conjunctions	Relative: Use the simple relative forms "que", "quien", and "cuanto". Replace the simple form "cuyo". Temporal: Preferably use "cuando" and "mientras". Locative: Use "donde". Modal: Use "como" and "según". Conditional: Use "si" and "por si", provided important logical expressions for financial texts are unaffected. Concessive: Use "aunque", or other frequently used ones such as "a pesar de que" and "incluso cuando".
10	Past anterior and future perfect tense	Use the forms of present, simple past, imperfect past, simple future, simple conditional, present perfect, pluperfect, and conditional perfect.
11	Subjunctive Mood Verb Forms	Limit the use of subjunctive to its forms of present, imperfect past, simple future, and pluperfect.
12	Use of Gerund	Replace the gerund forms in the sentences.
13	Abbreviations, Shortenings, Acronyms, and Initialisms	Use full expressions instead of abbreviations, shortenings, acronyms, and initialisms.
14	Use of Numerical Expressions	Write numerical expressions with letters.
15	Sentence Length	Use segments of 20 words or less. Dividing the discourse segment into several segments is recommended.
16	Parenthetical Phrases	Reserve use when they are essential for understanding the message.
17	Relative Clauses	Reduce the number of relative clauses per sentence (maximum one).
18	Sentences of formal and aesthetic use	Modify the use of these constructions when they are used solely for stylistic or aesthetic reasons.
19	Sentence Order	Preferably use the SVO order.
20	Common Discourse Markers	Use the most frequent markers in the cultural context.
21	Use of Complex Punctuation Marks	Eliminate using semicolons, brackets, dashes, single quotes, and angle quotes. Do not change the semicolon to period if the linguistic units separated with the first punctuation mark are words or phrases (enumerating lexical elements).

TABLE 14. Comparison of the spanish text simplification datasets.

Original	GPT-3	mT5	TUNER	FastChat	Alpaca13b	Llama 13b
Cuando se intenta definir el dinero, las personas piensan en monedas o billetes, lo cual es muy reducido porque el dinero es más que eso.	El dinero es más que monedas o billetes.	Cuando se intenta definir el dinero, las personas piensan en monedas o billetes, lo cual es muy reducido.	Cuando se intenta definir el dinero, las personas piensan en monedas o billetes, lo cual es muy reducido porque el dinero es más que eso.	Cuando se trata de definir el dinero, las personas piensan en monedas o billetes, pero el dinero es más que esos. No se trata sólo de monedas o billetes.	El dinero es un concepto más amplio que simplemente monedas o billetes. Se define como una mediodinero es más que eso. Se define como una mediodinero es más que eso.	The dinero es una forma de intercambiar bienes y servicios. Todos los bienes y servicios tienen un precio y se pueden comprar y vender. Algunos ejemplos de bienes son los hogares, los automóviles, los muebles de la casa, los alimentos y los cosméticos. Algunos ejemplos de servicios son la limpieza, la cocina, los negocios, la atención médica y la música.
A fin de mes, podrías tener unos \$50 para depositar en tu cuenta de ahorro, que suman \$600 al año (sin incluir los intereses, si los depositaras en una cuenta que pague intereses).	A fin de mes, podrías depositar \$50 en tu cuenta de ahorro, lo que sumará \$600 al año.	A fin de mes, podrías tener unos \$50 para depositar en tu cuenta de ahorro, que suman \$600 al año (sin incluir los intereses, si los depositaras en una cuenta que pague intereses).	A fin de mes, podrías tener unos \$50 para depositar en tu cuenta de ahorro. Esta tu cuenta de ahorro suman \$600 al año (sin admitir los intereses, si los depositaras en una cuenta). Esta una cuenta pague intereses.	A finales de mes, puedes tener \$50 para depositar en tu cuenta de ahorro, que puede agregarse a \$600 al año (sin incluir los intereses, si los encuentres en una cuenta que pague intereses).	Puedes tener unos \$50 para depositar en tu cuenta de ahorro, que suman \$600 al año (sin incluir los intereses, si los depositaras en una cuenta que pague intereses).	Fin de mes podrías tener unos \$50 para depositar en tu cuenta de ahorro, que suman \$600 al año (sin incluir los intereses, si los depositaras en una cuenta que pague intereses).
Ingresos de tipo residual: Son ingresos producto de rendimientos financieros, arriendos de bienes raíces, dividendos, acciones de empresas; es decir, las personas no tienen que realizar un trabajo para recibir su ingreso.	Ingresos residuales: se generan a partir de los rendimientos financieros, los arrendamientos de inmuebles, los dividendos y las acciones de las empresas; es decir, las personas no tienen que realizar un trabajo para obtener este ingreso.	Ingresos de tipo residual: Son ingresos producto de rendimientos financieros, arriendos de bienes raíces, dividendos, acciones de empresas; es decir, las personas no tienen que realizar ese tipo de transacciones.	Ingresos de tipo residual: Son ingresos producto de rendimientos financieros, arriendos de bienes raíces, dividendos, acciones de empresas; es decir, las personas no tienen que realizar un trabajo para recibir su ingreso.	Residuos residuales: Son medios de ingreso que no se llevarán en acciones o dividendos, y son hechos a causa de rendimientos financieros. Las personas no tienen que hacer trabajo para recibir estos medios.	Ingresos de tipo residual: Son ingresos producto de rendimientos financieros, arriendos de bienes raíces, dividendos, acciones de empresas; es decir, las personas no tienen que realizar un trabajo para recibir su ingreso.	Ingresos de tipo residual: Son ingresos producto de rendimientos financieros, arriendos de bienes raíces, dividendos, acciones de empresas; es decir, las personas no tienen que realizar un trabajo para recibir su ingreso.

to verify whether there is a statistically significant difference between the manual and GPT-3 metrics. In the same fashion as the results for the previous metrics set, we marked in Tables 9 and 10 the pairs of statistically similar results (using a $p = 0.05$ as criteria). According to the statistical analysis results, only the BLEU metric based comparison of the manual and GPT-3 systems can be considered not to be statistically different.

D. DISCRIMINATION BETWEEN COMPLEX AND SIMPLE VERSIONS

Table 11 shows the performance metrics of the models trained to classify text segments as complex or simple. Our assumption is that the classifier should yield higher

accuracy with better simplifications. Using the Wilcoxon test, we found that the Beto and Random Forest classifiers trained with the manually dataset, have better accuracy and F1 score than the models trained with the other datasets. Therefore, we can conclude that the manual dataset has more clear discrimination between simple and complex sentences. It is important to clarify that we considered the original text segments as complex because they had complex attributes that had to be simplified according to the advanced students in Philology.

On the other hand, we found that GPT-3 classifiers tend to get similar performance to turner classifiers, and better performance to mT5 with the exception of the accuracy in BETO. Therefore, we conclude that GPT-3 and Turner

discriminate between complex and simple text segments in a similar way.

E. HUMAN EVALUATION BASED METRICS

Table 12 presents the human judgment evaluation results, showing that both manual and GPT-3 datasets received similar and optimistic assessments. The first judge's average scores, being less than two or close to it, suggest that the simplified text segments from both datasets generally enhance the original texts in terms of simplicity, understandability, and appropriateness for blind people while retaining the original meaning. The second judge assigned slightly higher scores, still below 3, indicating similar improvements. While both datasets scored comparably, specific differences emerged: the manual dataset was rated higher for preserving original sentence meanings, whereas the GPT-3 dataset excelled in understandability. The other two datasets received lower ratings across all four dimensions; in many instances, the simplified versions were not deemed superior to the originals.

V. CONCLUSION

This study introduces Financial Education Corpus IN Spanish (FEINA), a comprehensive Spanish dataset designed explicitly for text simplification in the context of financial education for individuals with visual impairments. Developed through a meticulous manual simplification process, it comprises 5,314 pairs of complex and simplified sentences guided by structured linguistic rules. The dataset's effectiveness was validated through automatic and human-based evaluations, highlighting its relevance for NLP researchers and practitioners working on accessible technologies.

Our findings show that the manually simplified subset achieved the highest performance ($SARI \approx 48.7$), with GPT-3 coming close (≈ 41.6) and both scoring favorably in human evaluations (Likert ≈ 2.0 on a 5-point scale). By contrast, mT5 and TUNER yielded lower $SARI$ values (≈ 34.0 and ≈ 26.4 , respectively) and less favorable human ratings (Likert above 2.5). These results underscore the value of domain-focused corpora such as FEINA for maximizing the potential of large language models in specialized domains and improving real-world accessibility for visually impaired communities.

By openly releasing FEINA, we invite broader collaboration to extend the dataset's applicability to additional domains and foster more inclusive text simplification solutions. Future work will explore paragraph-level simplification and refine semantic preservation metrics to better address inter-sentence relationships and the complexity of longer financial texts. We anticipate these efforts will further empower literacy tools for individuals with visual impairments, advancing accessibility and social inclusion within NLP.

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APPENDIX

See Tables 13–14.

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